

Review

Exposure to radiofrequency electromagnetic fields and IARC carcinogen assessment: Risk of Bias preliminary literature assessment for 10 key characteristics of human carcinogens

Myrtill Simkó^{a,*}, Michael H. Repacholi^b, Kenneth R. Foster^c, Mats-Olof Mattsson^a,
Rodney J. Croft^d, Maria Rosaria Scarfi^e, Vijayalaxmi^f

^a SciProof International, Vaktpoststigen 4, Östersund 83158, Sweden

^b Department of Information Engineering, Electronics and Telecommunications (DIET), "La Sapienza" University of Rome, Rome 00184, Italy

^c Department of Bioengineering, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA, USA

^d Australian Centre for Electromagnetic Bioeffects Research, School of Psychology, University of Wollongong, Wollongong, New South Wales, Australia

^e Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment, National Research Council, Via Diocleziano, Naples 328-80124, Italy

^f Department of Radiology, University of Texas Health Science Center, San Antonio, TX, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Radiofrequency electromagnetic fields

Mechanisms

Key characteristics

Carcinogenesis

In vitro studies

In vivo studies

ABSTRACT

This is the first assessment of evidence needed to determine whether exposure to radiofrequency electromagnetic fields (RF-EMF) exposures, below the levels recommended in the ICNIRP (2020) guidelines, can influence any of the ten key characteristics (KCs) of human carcinogens developed by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). We define the 10 KCs and their relevance to carcinogenesis; review *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies relevant to the KCs; and conduct a risk of bias (RoB) analysis using 6 criteria. We did not include KC studies on genotoxicity or oxidative stress since Romeo et al. (2024) and Meyer et al. (2024) recently published relevant systematic reviews, but note their respective conclusions. From the other 8 KCs we identified 119 *in vitro* and 40 *in vitro* measurements of *in vivo* studies through 30 June 2023, with 38 % reporting statistically significant effects of exposure. We identified a strong association between the quality of study and outcome, with those meeting more RoB criteria less likely to report statistically significant effects. Effects were reported over the entire frequency range, exposure levels, and biological endpoints with no apparent pattern of exposure parameters resulting in effects. Only KC10 (alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply) has sufficient studies to analyse, but the other KCs had few studies and diverse endpoints. A few relatively high-quality positive studies require follow-up through additional targeted studies. The heterogeneity and overall poor study quality suggest the need for high-quality studies on these endpoints, preferably adhering to standards such as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [28].

1. Introduction

The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) is the World Health Organization's (WHO) specialized cancer agency, and part of its remit is to classify agents based on the strength of scientific evidence of their carcinogenicity. Recently, the title of the IARC Monographs series was changed to the IARC Monographs on the Identification of Carcinogenic Hazards to Humans [12]. This change is an important clarification because hazard identification is conducted within the Monographs, distinct from risk assessment where exposure response characterization is used to estimate cancer risk for a given scenario and

level of exposure. IARC also reduced the number of classifications of carcinogenicity of agents to 4 levels from the 5 used previously: Level "1: is carcinogenic, 2 A: is probably carcinogenic, 2B: is possibly carcinogenic, and 3: not classifiable" [37].

IARC amended its procedures for determining hazard classifications to give greater weight of evidence to mechanisms from *in vitro* studies that may help predict carcinogenicity in humans [12]. This change in classifying agents could be important for assessing the carcinogenicity of radiofrequency electromagnetic field (RF-EMF) exposure, which was classified as "2B – Possibly Carcinogenic" by IARC using their previous methodology, which was heavily weighted to epidemiological and *in*

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: myrtill.simko@sciproof-international.se (M. Simkó).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrrev.2025.108545>

Received 29 January 2025; Received in revised form 6 May 2025; Accepted 10 May 2025

Available online 27 May 2025

1383-5742/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

vivo studies [11]. Recently, an IARC Advisory Group recommended that RF-EMF fields be included in the IARC Monographs priorities during 2025–2029, to be assessed using IARC’s revised methodology [13].

IARC has identified 10 key characteristics (KCs) of human carcinogens [12]. These “physiological mechanisms” were based on the work of Smith et al. [43] and Guyton et al. [7]. IARC noted that assessments based on KCs need to consider how biologically significant the mechanistic endpoints actually are. Furthermore, IARC stresses that inter- and intra-individual variability, study quality, and study relevance are issues that are necessary to consider.

Table 1, adapted from Smith et al. [43], describes these characteristics along with examples of the types of experimental evidence required to support whether those characteristics are present. In Table 1, we briefly describe the 10 IARC KCs and present examples of how relevant each of the KCs is for carcinogenesis. It is important to note that small changes in endpoints, particularly those observed in *in vitro* studies, related to the various KCs will not necessarily imply the carcinogenicity of an agent in living animals. Accordingly, studies need to take into account the normal repair and compensatory systems within the body when evaluating carcinogenicity. However, evidence that agents influence several KCs can underpin mechanistic findings. For example, “induces oxidative stress” together with “is electrophilic or can be metabolically activated to an electrophile”, or “induces chronic inflammation” together with “is immunosuppressive” provides greater confidence in an agent’s carcinogenicity [12]. In addition, in Table 1 more attention was dedicated to the KCs that are relevant to the present paper.

There has also been a shift in recent years towards more rigorous methods to assess the scientific literature for health risk assessments, including the use of systematic reviews (SRs) and meta-analyses. The WHO [47] handbook states that health guidelines “should be supported by one or more systematic reviews of the evidence...[which] should be reported in a standard format using the PRISMA [Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses] reporting guidelines”.

WHO now requires, in addition to the assessment of risk of bias (RoB) for individual studies, assessment of consistency of results across studies, indirectness (relevance to a specific health endpoint), imprecision (variance in results across studies), and possible publication bias. For a summary of the PRISMA guidelines see Page et al. [29]. Preparation of PRISMA-compliant SRs is a major undertaking, typically requiring teams of investigators a year or more to complete.

Of the 10 KCs, we are aware of only two PRISMA-compliant reviews on the KCs, namely oxidative stress [23] and genotoxicity [35]. We presently assess the extent and quality of literature related to the other 8 KCs, but do not attempt a full SR of this body of evidence. We focus on whether statistically significant effects have been reported in relevant studies, which would be central to a future IARC hazard identification. To the extent possible, full SRs of this literature are needed.

1.1. Risk of Bias (RoB) assessment

The PRISMA guidelines [29] call for a rigorous RoB analysis, which is typically done using guidelines developed by the U.S. National Toxicology Program’s Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT), [25,26]. For our analysis, we applied 6 RoB criteria to all studies; Table 2 was used previously by Simkó et al. [41], and Foster and Vijayalaxmi [5]. These RoB criteria generally address the internal validity of a study, but they are also useful surrogates for study quality; however, a full assessment of study quality requires a broader assessment [38].

The Robins-E [10] to evaluate RoB is mainly applicable for epidemiological studies, and so the RoB assessment procedures are not generally applicable for laboratory studies. However, as required by Robins-E, we did identify RoB criteria appropriate to laboratory studies, and ordered them, as shown in Table 2. They were mostly simple yes or no answers. For example, did the study use sham or positive controls, or was it blinded? So, assessment of RoB using our criteria was

Table 1

Key characteristics (KCs) of human carcinogens (partly quoted, cited and modified from [43]*.

Key characteristics (KCs)	Examples of relevant evidence, a short description of the respective KC, and its link to carcinogenesis
KC1. Is electrophilic or can be metabolically activated to an electrophile	Examples: Parent compound or metabolite with an electrophilic structure (e.g., epoxide, quinone), formation of DNA and protein adducts Description: “The ability to form adducts on nucleic acids and proteins is a common property of inherently electrophilic and/or metabolically activated human carcinogens” [42].
KC2. Is genotoxic	Examples: DNA damage (DNA strand breaks, DNA–protein cross-links, unscheduled DNA synthesis), intercalation, gene mutations, cytogenetic changes (e.g., chromosome aberrations, micronuclei) Description: DNA damage occurs in cells every day, estimated to be at least 70,000 events per cell daily Lindahl and Barnes [21], thus DNA mechanisms exist to repair this amount of damage. In cases of dysfunction in repair mechanisms, DNA damage could lead to carcinogenesis .
KC3. Alters DNA repair or causes genomic instability	Examples: Alterations of DNA replication or repair (e.g., topoisomerase II, base-excision or double-strand break repair) Description: The replication accuracy of DNA can vary significantly depending on whether the DNA polymerase (repair enzyme) introduces mistakes, especially when certain DNA repair and/or checkpoints are inactivated, DNA editing enzymes are deregulated, or the damage load exceeds the DNA reconstruction capacity [45]. Genomic instability is normally defined as higher-than-normal rates or an increased tendency for DNA mutations, or other genetic changes that can appear during cell division. Such genomic defects can give rise to strong mutation phenotypes (potent mutator phenotypes), which consequently can introduce genomic instability, leading to carcinogenesis [18]. The induction of genomic instability in the form of increased mutation rate, apoptosis, chromosomal aberrations, micronuclei and other damage requires damage in cell generations after exposure, in the non-exposed progeny of the exposed cells [9].
KC4. Induces epigenetic alterations	Examples: DNA methylation, histone modification, microRNA expression Description: Epigenetic changes are not caused by changes in the DNA, but are stable modifications of gene expression and chromatin organization. They generally consist of histone variants, post-translational modifications of amino acids at the amino-terminal tail of histones and covalent modifications of DNA structures, X-chromosome inactivation, and the reconfiguration of DNA methylation. Epigenetic phenomena include genomic imprinting (a process where only one gene copy is expressed). These changes can occur during development and have the potential to contribute to the lineage-specific epigenome, which is maintained throughout an organism’s lifespan [42]. Epigenetic changes are reversible and do not change the DNA sequence. However, they can change how the DNA sequence is read causing the initiation/promotion of cancer [2].
KC5. Induces oxidative stress	Examples: Oxygen radicals, oxidative stress, oxidative damage to macromolecules (e.g.,

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Key characteristics (KCs)	Examples of relevant evidence,a short description of the respective KC, and its link to carcinogenesis
KC6. Induces chronic inflammation	<p>DNA, lipids) Description: Oxidative stress is caused by an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the antioxidant enzymes that scavenge these free radicals in the biological systems. ROS are products of normal cellular oxygen metabolism and play vital roles in the stimulation of signaling pathways [33]. Antioxidant defenses normally eliminate excessive ROS in cells, neutralizing them with endogenous antioxidants such as reduced glutathione (GSH), α-tocopherol, vitamin C, and other antioxidant enzyme systems [32], such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), thioredoxin 1 (TRX1) and peroxiredoxin 2 (PRX2) catalase, GSH-Px, or prooxidant enzymes such as xanthine oxidase (XO). These molecules play an important role in balancing ROS levels [22]. Oxidative stress is considered a major factor for DNA mutations (point mutations, deletions, insertions, or chromosomal translocations). These changes can cause oncogene activation, tumour suppressor inactivation, and other relevant DNA mutations, that potentially initiate or promote carcinogenesis. [1,17]. However, oxidative stress does not necessarily lead to cancer, although there is a strong correlation between these two phenomena. Thus, it is necessary to distinguish between processes that change redox homeostasis and those that activate signaling processes [40, 8]. The direct detection of most reactive oxidants is difficult as they have a short half-life. Therefore, the detection of oxidative stress is mainly based on the measurement of their oxidation products on DNA, lipids, and proteins [4]. Such biomarkers include nitric oxide (NO), increased levels of malondialdehyde (indicative of lipid peroxidation), or reduction in glutathione (GSH). Examples: Elevated white blood cells, myeloperoxidase activity, altered cytokine and/or chemokine production Description: The inflammatory process begins when blood cells such as macrophages and neutrophils migrate to the area of damage or infection and release pro-inflammatory substances (chemokines and cytokines) that promote recovery by helping to overcome harmful stressors [24], ending with the healing of the injury. For chronic inflammation, the inflammation process continues. Chronic inflammation is due to persistent infection or irritation and is associated with various types of cancer. This mechanism could also alter cell signaling by disrupting local tissue homeostasis, leading to the recruitment and activation of inflammatory cells [48]. No highly effective laboratory measures exist to distinguish between acute and chronic inflammation. Some tests provide indications of chronic inflammation [30], such as serum protein electrophoresis (SPE) that shows concomitant hypoalbuminemia and polyclonal increase in all gamma globulins (polyclonal gammopathy). Blood tests that are good markers of systemic inflammation are the measurements of the high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hsCRP, as an indicator</p>

Table 1 (continued)

Key characteristics (KCs)	Examples of relevant evidence,a short description of the respective KC, and its link to carcinogenesis
KC7. Is immunosuppressive	<p>for inflammation in general) and fibrinogen. The measurement of pro-inflammatory cytokines like tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-alpha), interleukin-1beta (IL-1beta), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-8 (IL-8) can also identify chronic inflammation. However, given the close relationship between inflammation and the induction of oxidative stress and genomic instability, differentiation between mechanisms that play a role in carcinogenesis is very difficult [48]. Examples: Decreased immunosurveillance, immune system dysfunction Description: Immunosuppression is the suppression of the body's defense system. It is a process that suppresses the immunological activity of the humoral and/or cellular immune system. The immune system can no longer react adequately to foreign antigens (e.g. antigens on tumor cells), and can be suppressed by the death of immune effector cells or the blocking of intracellular pathways that are essential for antigen recognition or other elements of the immune response [34]. Prolonged immunosuppression represents a considerable health risk, especially if it is accompanied by exposure to foreign antigens, such as a virus that causes cancer [44]. Although the suppression of the immune system does not directly transform healthy cells into tumor cells, this mechanism significantly reduces immune surveillance. As a result, the survival of these cells and their proliferation into tumors becomes strongly facilitated [19]. Examples: Receptor in/activation (e.g., aryl hydrocarbon receptor AhR; estrogen receptor ER; peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor PPAR) or modulation of endogenous ligands (including hormones) Description: Receptor-mediated action is a cellular process in which certain molecules are taken up into the cell after binding to receptor proteins on the cell membrane. The modulation of receptor-mediated effects can arise when drugs imitate the structure of endogenous ligands. They can then bind to the cell surface or intracellular receptors and activate them. This can initiate or modify signal transduction pathways that can stimulate cell proliferation [18]. Receptor-mediated activation usually leads to changes in gene transcription. The molecular processes most relevant to carcinogenesis include cell proliferation, xenobiotic metabolism, and the modulation of the bioavailability of endogenous ligands by influencing their biosynthesis, bioactivation, and degradation [3]. Examples: Inhibition of senescence, cell transformation Description: Immortalization means that cells escape cellular senescence and can reproduce indefinitely. Telomeres preserve genomic integrity, however, their successive shortening at consecutive cell divisions leads to senescence and chromosomal instability. Cells become immortalized by turning on the production of telomerase that they normally don't produce, allowing them to keep their long telomeres indefinitely [39]. In most</p>
KC8. Modulates receptor-mediated effects	
KC9. Causes immortalization	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Key characteristics (KCs)	Examples of relevant evidence,a short description of the respective KC, and its link to carcinogenesis
KC10. Alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply	<p>cancer cells, telomere length is preserved by the enzyme telomerase, and consequently, telomere length, and telomerase activity are relevant for the tumor development and survival [15]. Transcriptional, post-transcriptional, and epigenetic mechanisms are involved in the perpetuation of telomere length and telomerase expression [39].</p> <p>Examples: Increased proliferation, decreased apoptosis, changes in growth factors, energetics and signalling pathways related to cellular replication or cell cycle control, angiogenesis</p> <p>Description: Alterations in cell proliferation and/or cell cycle control are important factors in the development of cancer. These include unrepaired DNA damage that leads to mutations in proliferating cells, which in turn can cause cancer. Sustained replication of these cells leads to transformed cells with the ability to develop and proliferate out of cell cycle control [43]. One component common to all scenarios is the bypassing of apoptosis or autophagy [36]. The family of caspase enzymes (cysteine proteases) starts the chain reaction that leads to a cell's death by apoptosis. Caspases act like molecular scissors and are inactive in normal cells. When a cell is under stress or programmed to activate apoptosis, caspases activate and remove or cleave certain proteins inside the cell to start the apoptosis process. In cancer cells, caspases may not receive the signal to cut if the sensor gene (e. g. the p53 gene), which is supposed to recognize cell damage, is not functioning or the signal is never sent. Mutations in the p53 gene have been found in around 50 % of all types of cancer [6,20]. Autophagy is another form of programmed cell death, in which a cell breaks down and digests itself. It is a natural and important part of growth and development. It can also be a response to certain diseases or stress, such as infection. In cases where autophagy is not activated at the right time, cells can grow in an uncontrolled fashion [6,20]. For this KC to be active the agent needs to increase proliferation, decrease apoptosis, change growth factors, energetics, or signaling pathways related to cellular replication or cell cycle control, or cause angiogenesis. An example is ornithine decarboxylase (ODC), the first and rate-limiting enzyme in the polyamine biosynthesis pathway. Polyamines are involved in the control of the cell cycle, and also in cell differentiation. Tumor promoters such as TPA induce ODC activity, making changes in cellular ODC activity important for carcinogenesis. A high level of ODC activity has been found in several premalignant conditions [11].</p>

* For readability, quotations and adaptations from Smith et al. [43], such as the “KCs”, “examples” and some of the descriptions are not specifically indicated.

straightforward. Our team also included expertise in electronic engineering and physics, thus assessment of the exposure system and dosimetry were determined if sufficient information was provided by the authors. The judgments and basic data about each study (exposure

Table 2

Simplified risk of bias (RoB) criteria for in vitro and in vivo studies.

RoB criteria	Description
C1: Use of sham controls	Sham-exposed controls (control groups in the same equipment and environmental conditions without exposure to RF-EMF) are needed to simulate identical exposure conditions. Sham controls are obligatory to attribute effects to the exposure.
C2: Use of positive controls	Positive controls (controls treated with a well-known agent that induces the effect under investigation) show whether the chosen experimental methods are appropriate and sensitive enough to assess the endpoint. For in vivo studies, there are historical outcomes that can be used as positive controls.
C3: Use of negative controls	Negative controls (generally controls with samples placed in incubators with no other intervention) provide information on the background level of the endpoint under examination. For in vivo studies, there are historical controls that can be used for negative controls.
C4: Appropriate temperature control	Adequate temperature control within the sample that is recorded during exposure to RF-EMF can allow the identification of non-thermal effects from those due to heating.
C5: Blinding	Blinding scientists to which groups are exposed/non-exposed, as well as to the final analyses, are needed to avoid individual/observer bias.
C6: Appropriate dosimetry	A detailed and adequate description of dosimetry should provide the necessary information which allows replication and/ or confirmation studies by independent laboratories. Studies using mobile phones or similar devices are deemed inappropriate as sources of exposure (because of the potential lack of proper dosimetry).

Adapted from Simkó et al. [41], Foster and Vijayalaxmi, [5].

levels and frequencies, biological endpoint) are shown in the Appendix. If a study reported at least one statistically significant effect, it was considered positive.

Sham (C1) and negative controls (C3) differ in the level of intervention with the exposed animal or cells [16]. A sham control undergoes a procedure that mimics the treatment but absent actual exposure to the agent. Negative controls receive no treatment related to the experimental variable (no RF-EMF exposure) and are used as a comparator for positive controls. Thus, in an in vivo RF bioeffects study, a negative control might be a group of animals housed in a room separate from the exposure facility but matched to the exposed animals for age and sex, while sham controls would be housed in a chamber identical to that used to expose the animals, but not exposed to RF fields. In an in vitro study, a sham control would be subjected to all experimental manipulations without exposure to RF fields. Meyer et al. [23] and Romeo et al. [35] used similar quality criteria, together with additional assessments following a rigorous procedure that is explained in detail in their papers. These authors grouped studies into three Tiers of decreasing quality. This quality assessment was not directly used in a numerical analysis/meta-analysis of the study results but was used to determine the overall confidence of the teams of reviewers in their final assessments.

The RoB criteria in Table 2 address the internal validity of studies, i. e. whether the reported changes associated with exposure were causally related to the exposure. Studies can (and should) be evaluated in a different framework as well, which broadly considers whether the study management was sufficient to produce reliable and reproducible results. Toxicology studies for submission to regulatory agencies are typically required to follow Good Laboratory Practices (GLP), a burdensome set of procedures involving detailed standard operating procedures, pre-specified protocols for acquiring and evaluating data, policies for dealing with outlying data points, etc. [27]. As is the case with most academic research, few if any of the studies presently reviewed were done under GLP or equivalent standards for reproducibility and

reliability, and the documentation in the published papers was frequently inadequate to allow judgment of the rigor of the work in any event.

1.2. Purpose of this review

Given the use of RF-EMF fields for communications and many other applications requiring data transfer, and the fact that virtually everyone in the world is now exposed to RF-EMF at various levels, it is important to fully assess any possible health impacts. Cancer from these fields has been of particular concern. Since IARC has already classified RF-EMF exposure as a “possible carcinogen”, it is necessary to regularly evaluate whether there is sufficient quality evidence to respond to this concern.

The strength of RF-EMF energy is too low to break macromolecular bonds. Thus, RF-EMF at or below the ICNIRP [14] limits has no credible mechanism for direct DNA damage that could lead to cancer. As such, IARC has identified 10 “physiological mechanisms” or key characteristics (KCs) that could be activated by an agent and lead to cancer in the exposed organism. So, the purpose of this review is to determine whether there is any quality evidence to suggest that RF-EMF exposure could lead to carcinogenesis.

2. Material and methods

Search criteria: Our review considered original *in vitro* cancer studies, as well as results from *in vitro* analyses of *in vivo* studies that involved RF-EMF exposure but excluded studies relevant to the two KCs previously reviewed by Meyer et al. [23] and Romeo et al. [35]. Scientific databases were searched using the following terms: Radio-frequency fields, high frequency, microwaves, mm waves, plus *in vitro* studies and/or *in vitro* analyses of *in vivo* studies plus any of the following endpoints: genotoxicity, genomic instability, cell proliferation, and cell cycle, immune response, oxidative stress, apoptosis, gene and protein expression, and transformation. Searches for relevant literature were conducted on EMF-Portal, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Previous reviews were also searched for additional studies. The cut-off date for studies included in this review is 30 June 2023.

Inclusion/exclusion criteria: *In vitro* cancer studies or *in vitro* analyses of animal carcinogenesis assays exposed to RF-EMF fields at frequencies between 300 MHz and 300 GHz, with or without modulation, were identified using the search terms and assessment criteria above. Papers were limited to those published in English in peer-reviewed scientific journals, that were determined to be appropriate tests for the endpoints/KCs.

All studies were examined for their exposure conditions. Studies using mobile telephone handsets or similar devices for exposure were not considered, because of the potential lack of reproducible dosimetry (either due to the complex radiation patterns from the devices or due to network control of their power output; and/or because the power was not carefully controlled and the exposure properties have not been taken into account properly in the dosimetric analysis). Abstracts and conference presentations were not considered. Meta-analyses, pooled analyses, and earlier reviews were not used for the primary analysis.

Analysis of Studies: Basic information about each study was entered on separate lines of Excel worksheets (presented as Microsoft Word documents in the Appendix), with separate worksheets for each KC, and separating *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. Each worksheet includes the study reference, a description of the exposed system (animal/cell model used), endpoint(s) measured, RF-EMF frequency and specific absorption rate (SAR), exposure duration, whether a study reported a statistically significant effect (yes/no), compliance with the 6 RoB criteria separately, the number of independent experiment repeats (n), and comments by the reviewers. No attempt was made to extract the effect size from the papers. The number of studies in the tables is somewhat larger than the number of publications since several studies investigated

multiple endpoints that were relevant to different KCs. All extracted *in vivo* and *in vitro* data regarding the 8 KCs are presented in the [Supplementary Materials: Table S1](#). List of selected publications and extracted experimental parameters related to the 8 Key Characteristics (KCs) of Human Carcinogens after exposure to RF-EMF *in vitro*. [Table S2](#). List of selected publications and extracted experimental parameters related to the 8 Key Characteristics (KCs) of Human Carcinogens after exposure to RF-EMF *in vivo*.

For studies using more than one exposure level and/or RF frequency, only exposures (in terms of specific absorption rate or SAR) at or below 4 W/kg were included. A few studies reported exposure in terms of quantities other than SAR (e.g., incident power density); these data were included in the worksheets. Effects reported only after co-exposure with another agent were not considered in our analysis. Endpoints were grouped into their corresponding KC(s): Gene and protein expression data were included into their related KC, such as “Modulates receptor-mediated effects” and “Alters cell proliferation, cell death (apoptosis) or nutrient supply”. Data from apoptosis was considered as an effect if this endpoint decreased since an increase was not seen as an effect relevant to carcinogenesis. For analyses and plotting of results, we used Microsoft Excel and Matlab (MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA). The workflow is shown in [Fig. 1](#).

[Fig. 2](#) shows the distribution of publication dates of the studies presently considered. The number of relevant studies has roughly doubled since the earlier review [11].

3. Results

Distribution of studies by KC and study quality. [Table 3](#) summarizes the number of *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies and the number of “positive” studies for each of the 8 KCs we reviewed. Only one of the 8 KCs, KC10 (Alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply), had a comparable number of studies to those examined in the Meyer et al. [23] or Romeo et al. [35] reviews.

[Table 3](#) shows that, overall, the vast majority of higher-quality studies (meeting the 5/6 RoBs) were negative. Sixty-eight of the 179 studies (38 %) reported statistically significant effects, and of the 29 studies meeting the 5/6 RoBs, only 3 (10 %) were positive. Similarly, for the 129 studies on KC10: “alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply”, 30 studies (23 %) reported a statistically significant effect, but none of these met the 5/6 RoBs. Similar findings have been reported in several previous reviews (e.g. [46], [41], as well as in [35]).

The overall failure to meet what would be considered good experimental design is striking.

[Fig. 3](#) shows the fraction of studies meeting each of the RoB criteria. A majority of studies failed to meet (or at least failed to describe meeting) three RoB criteria (C2, C3, C5). In part, this may reflect limitations in the documentation of studies, which were often reported in brief papers, or (as we believe) simple poor practice.

We have made a robust argument against the use of the ‘vote counting’ approach to evidence synthesis. The majority of studies on oxidative stress reported statistically significant effects of exposure; however, the proportion of positive studies decreased in studies that were more rigorous (i.e. that met a greater number of RoB criteria). This result represents a central conclusion of our review. This result is also confirmed by the conclusions of Meyer et al. [23] and Romeo et al. [35], who also observed a decrease in the proportion of positive studies in studies with higher RoB values.

We examined whether an obvious pattern existed with reported effects vs. exposure level and detected, that most studies used frequencies employed by cellular telephone systems (variously near 900, 950, 1800, 1900 MHz), a few used 2450 MHz (the industrial scientific medical band used by Wi-Fi and other technologies) and a scattering used other frequencies.

Studies reported multiple exposures (varying frequency and exposure level (given as specific absorption rate (SAR))). There were also few

Fig. 1. Flow chart showing each step from the literature search to the analysis of the studies.

Fig. 2. Distribution of studies for 8 KCs presently reviewed by year of publication.

Table 3

Number of in vitro and in vivo studies assessed for each of the 8 analyzed IARC KCs, and whether they reported a statistically significant effect of exposure.

Key characteristics	Total in vivo studies	All studies reporting statistically significant effects	Studies meeting 5 or 6 RoB C	Positive studies meeting 5 or 6 RoB C	Total in vitro studies	Number of studies reporting statistically significant effects	Studies meeting 5 or 6 RoB C	Positive studies meeting 5 or 6 RoB C
Electrophilic or metabolic	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Genotoxicity	Covered in Romeo et al. [35]							
DNA repair or causes genomic instability	4	4	0	0	5	5	0	0
Epigenetic alterations	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
Oxidative stress	Covered in Meyer et al. [23]							
Chronic inflammation	0	0	0	0	10	8	0	0
Immuno-suppressive-Immune response	17	12	1	0	0	0	0	0
Receptor-mediated effects	1	1	0	0	2	2	1	1
Immortal-ization	0	0	0	0	8	3	2	2
Alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply	19	9	2	0	110	21	23	0
Total	43	28	3	0	136	42	26	3

Empty cells (“0”) indicate that no studies were identified in the review or that no studies met the 5/6 RoB criteria (RoB C).

studies reporting exposure in terms of incident power density which were chiefly at the higher frequencies, typically > 5 GHz. Strikingly, effects were reported over the entire range of frequencies and exposure levels employed, with no apparent demarcation separating positive from negative studies. This suggests the absence of a relationship between KCs and exposure. The simplest explanation is that some or most of the “positive” findings were affected by bias, particularly the lower-quality studies. Other explanations may be possible: the studies using the lowest exposure levels (SARs) typically used longer-term exposures. For the largest group of studies, further evaluation including consideration of

effect size might yield SAR/exposure duration relationships that are not apparent.

4. Discussion

Since the conclusion of the last IARC carcinogen review for RF-EMF [11] in 2011–12, the number of in vivo and in vitro bioeffects studies in the literature has more than doubled. Nevertheless, the number of studies related to 7 of the 10 KCs remains very scant; and for all the KCs considered here, the relevant literature remains very mixed and

Fig. 3. Fraction of studies meeting different RoB criteria (C). Data are shown separately for KC10 and the 8 KCs combined in the included studies.

generally of poor quality.

From Table 3, there appears to be a sufficient number of studies to support a SR on a third KC (alters cell proliferation, cell death or nutrient supply) in addition to Romeo et al. [35] and Meyer et al. [23], although such a SR would face similar limitations as the two completed SRs (chiefly, overall poor quality of the studies). For the remaining 7 KCs, the literature is too scant to permit an extensive SR. We conclude that none of these groups of studies would permit any conclusions about effects of RF-EMF on the respective endpoints with high confidence, although the preponderance of negative studies with higher quality suggests that no such effects are readily apparent or exist at all. The overall small size of the studies, with a median of about 5 experimental units per study, means that the studies had generally low statistical power, and conceivably small effects might be present but not resolved by the studies.

The strong negative association between study quality (presently assessed in terms of RoB criteria) and the likelihood of reporting effects has an important implication for reviews of literature in this field: “vote counting”, i.e. comparing numbers of positive vs. negative effects without attention to risk of bias and other quality issues, will yield unreliable and quite likely misleading results about the possible effects of RF-EMF on biological systems.

In our review, a small number (5 of 40) of the highest quality studies (meeting 5 or 6 RoB criteria) reported statistically significant effects. Similarly, in the SR on genotoxicity [35] 7 of the 39 highest quality papers (Tier 1), out of a total of 159 papers considered, reported statistically significant effects. The other SR, by Meyer et al. [23], classified only one paper in Tier 1. These Tier 1 studies need further examination and replication by more rigorous follow-up studies, preferably under GLP or otherwise using methods consistent with OHAT recommendations. Health agencies might consider commissioning high-quality studies on the other KCs, although we suggest that focused research on endpoints of more immediate health significance should have a higher priority.

Our present observations are consistent with the conclusions of the full SRs by Romeo et al. [35] and Meyer et al. [23]. Concerning genotoxicity, Romeo et al. [35] conclude:

“...we reached an overall assessment of “low” confidence in the level of evidence that RF-EMF induce genotoxic effects in mammalian cells. However, 80 % of experiments reviewed showed no effect of RF exposure on the large majority of endpoints... independently of the exposure features, level, and duration (moderate evidence of no effect)... [This review]... suggests that RF exposure does not increase the occurrence of genotoxic effects in vitro.”

With respect to oxidative stress, Meyer et al. [23] conclude:

“The evidence on the relation between the exposure to RF-EMF and biomarkers of oxidative stress was of very low certainty, because a majority of the included studies were rated with a high RoB level and provided high heterogeneity. This is due to inaccurate measurements of exposure and/or of measurement of oxidative stress biomarkers and missing information on the blinding of the research personnel. There may be no or an inconsistent effect of RF-EMF on biomarkers... but the evidence is of very low certainty...”

5. Limitation of the review

A significant limitation of the present review is that it was not a PRISMA-compliant systematic review or scoping review. However, the present review did not fully adhere to the standard guidelines for a scoping review, although our approach bore some similarities to the approach adopted in Peters et al. [31]. It is not feasible to adjust the present review (eight reviews in total) to conform to such guidelines. This limitation is acknowledged, and the necessity for comprehensive scoping reviews and, where applicable, SRs, is emphasized.

6. Conclusions

This review aimed to assess the extent and adequacy of experimental data bearing on whether exposure to RF-EMF could influence any of the 10 IARC key characteristics of human carcinogenesis. Since two PRISMA-compliant SRs on the KCs genotoxicity and oxidative stress were recently published [35,23], this present review was limited to the 8 remaining KCs for which no systematic reviews have been conducted so far. It became apparent that the present database of in vitro and in vivo studies was so diverse and scattered in their quality that helpful outcomes of SRs on most of the KCs would be unfeasible, and any conclusions from such reviews would have a very low confidence. The two PRISMA-compliant SRs as well as previous comprehensive reviews on in vitro and in vivo genotoxicity studies (e.g. [46], and our review of studies on the 8 KCs, have all reached the same conclusion: there is clearly a need for much higher quality RF-EMF bioeffects studies on these KCs.

There are, however, a few statistically significant results in the highest quality studies (Tier 1 studies in Romeo et al. [35] and studies meeting 5 or 6 RoB criteria (present study). These deserve close examination, and replication if warranted by stronger studies, preferably done under GLP [28], or are otherwise compliant with OHAT recommendations.

As a final comment, it is not useful for systematic reviews to examine hundreds of papers on a given topic, only to find that the overall quality

of the large majority of the studies is too low to permit conclusions with a high level of confidence.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael H Repacholi: Conceptualization. **Myrtil Simkó, Mats-Olof Mattsson, Kenneth R Foster, Michael H Repacholi, Maria Rosaria Scarfi, Rodney J Croft, Vijayalaxmi:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Acquisition and Curation, Writing. **Kenneth R Foster:** Visualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

Authors MS, MOM, and MRS acknowledge funding from the Next-GEM project from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057527 for part of this study. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The other authors received no external funding for this research.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.mrrrev.2025.108545](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrrrev.2025.108545).

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- B.R. Berquist, D.M. Wilson 3rd, Pathways for repairing and tolerating the spectrum of oxidative DNA lesions, 2012 Dec 31, *Cancer Lett.* 327 (1-2) (2012) 61–72, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2012.12.012>.
- CDC, What is epigenetics? genomic precision and health. center for disease control, CDC, 2020. (<https://www.cdc.gov/genomics/disease/epigenetics.htm>).
- H. Ellinger-Ziegelbauer, B. Stuart, B. Wahle, W. Boman, H.-J. Ahr, Characteristic expression profiles induced by genotoxic carcinogens in rat liver, *Toxicol. Sci.* 77 (1) (2004) 19–34, <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfh016>.
- H.J. Forman, O. Augusto, R. Brigelius-Flohe, P.A. Dennery, B. Kalyanaraman, H. Ischiropoulos, G.E. Mann, R. Radi, I.L.J. Roberts, J. Vina, Even free radicals should follow some rules: a guide to free radical research terminology and methodology, *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 78 (2015) 233–235.
- K.R. Foster, Vijayalaxmi, Needed: more reliable bioeffects studies at “high band” 5g frequencies, *Front. Comms. Net.* 2 (2021) 721925, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frcmn.2021.721925>.
- J. Grisham, 2014, What is apoptosis? News and Information. Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (<https://www.mskcc.org/news/what-apoptosis>) Accessed 07.01.2025.
- K.Z. Guyton, I. Rusyn, W.A. Chiu, D.E. Corpet, M. van den Berg, M.K. Ross, D. C. Christiani, F.A. Beland, M.T. Smith, Application of the key characteristics of carcinogens in cancer hazard identification, *Carcinogenesis* 39 (2018) 614–622.
- B. Henschenmacher, A. Bitsch, T. de Las Heras Gala, H.J. Forman, A. Fragoulis, P. Ghezzi, R. Kellner, W. Koch, J. Kuhne, D. Sachno, The effect of radiofrequency electromagnetic fields (RF-EMF) on biomarkers of oxidative stress in vivo and in vitro: a protocol for a systematic review, *Environ. Int.* 158 (2022) 106932.
- M. Herrala, E. Mustafa, J. Naarala, J. Juutilainen, Assessment of genotoxicity and genomic instability in rat primary astrocytes exposed to 872 MHz radiofrequency radiation and chemicals (Available at:), *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.* 94 (10) (2018) 883–889, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09553002.2018.1450534>.
- J.P.T. Higgins, R.L. Morgan, A.A. Rooney, K.W. Taylor, K.A. Thayer, R.A. Silva, C. Lemeris, E.A. Akl, T.F. Bateson, N.D. Berkman, B.S. Glenn, A. Hróbjartsson, J. S. LaKind, A. McAleenan, J.J. Meerpohl, R.M. Nachman, J.E. Obbagy, A. O’Connor, E.G. Radke, J. Savović, H.J. Schünemann, B. Shea, K. Tilling, J. Verbeek, M. Viswanathan, J.A.C. Sterne, A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of exposure effects (ROBINS-E) (Apr), *Environ. Int.* 186 (2024) 108602, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108602>.
- IARC. Non-ionizing radiation Part 2: Radiofrequency electromagnetic fields, Monograph Series, 102, International Agency on Research on Cancer, Lyon, France, 2013.
- IARC, Preamble: IARC monographs on the identification of carcinogenic hazards to humans, International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France, 2019.
- IARC, Report of the advisory group to recommend priorities for the iarc monographs during 2025-2029, International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France, 2024. (<https://www.iarc.who.int/news-events/advisory-group-recommendations-on-priorities-for-the-iarc-monographs-during-2025-2029/>) (Available at:).
- ICNIRP, Guidelines for limiting exposure to electromagnetic fields (100 kHz to 300 GHz) international commission on non-ionizing radiation protection (ICNIRP), *Health Phys.* 118 (5) (2020) 483–524.
- M.A. Jafri, S.A. Ansari, M.H. Alqahtani, J.W. Shay, Roles of telomeres and telomerase in cancer, and advances in telomerase targeted therapies, *Genome Med.* 8 (2016) 69, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-016-0324-x>.
- P.D. Johnson, D.G. Besselsen, Practical aspects of experimental design in animal research, 2002, *ILAR J.* 43 (4) (2002) 202–206, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ilar.43.4.202>. PMID: 12391395.
- J.E. Klaunig, Z. Wang, X. Pu, S. Zhou, Oxidative stress and oxidative damage in chemical carcinogenesis, 15, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharm.* 254 (2) (2011) 86–99, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2009.11.028>.
- D. Krewski, M. Bird, M. Al-Zoughool, N. Birkett, M. Billarda, B. Milton, J.M. Rice, J. Grosse, V.J. Coglian, M.A. Hill, R.A. Baan, J. Little, J.M. Zielinski, Key characteristics of 86 agents known to cause cancer in humans, *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health, Part B* 22 (7–8) (2019) 244–263, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2019.1643536>.
- J.K. Kundu, Y.-J. Surh, Emerging avenues linking inflammation and cancer, *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 52 (9) (2013) 2013–2037.
- A. Letai, Apoptosis and cancer, *Annu. Rev. Cancer Biol.* 1 (2017) 275–294. (<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev-cancerbio-050216-121933>). Accessed 07.01.2025).
- T. Lindahl, D.E. Barnes, Repair of endogenous DNA damage, *Cold Spring Harb. Symp. Quant. Biol.* 65 (2000) 127–133 [PubMed: 12760027].
- J.P. McNamee, V.S. Grybas, S.S. Qutob, P.V. Bellier, Effects of 1800 MHz radiofrequency fields on signal transduction and antioxidant proteins in human A172 glioblastoma cells, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.* 97 (9) (2021) 1316–1323, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09553002.2021.1934751>.
- F. Meyer, A. Bitsch, H.J. Forman, A. Fragoulis, P. Ghezzi, B. Henschenmacher, R. Kellner, J. Kuhne, T. Ludwig, D. Sachno, The effects of radiofrequency electromagnetic field exposure on biomarkers of oxidative stress in vivo and in vitro: A systematic review of experimental studies, *Environ. Int.* (2024) 108940.
- M. Nigam, A.P. Mishra, V.K. Deb, D.B. Dimri, V. Tiwari, S.G. Bungua, A.F. Bungua, A.F. Radu, Evaluation of the association of chronic inflammation and cancer: insights and implications, *Biomed. Pharm.* 164 (2023) 115015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2023.115015>. Epub 2023 Jun 13. PMID: 37321055.
- NTP (2015). OHAT Risk of Bias Rating Tool for Human and Animal Studies. Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT) Division of the National Toxicology Program (NTP). Available at: (https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/sites/default/files/ntp/ohat/pubs/riskofbiastool_508.pdf).
- NTP, Handbook for conducting a literature-based health assessment using OHAT approach for systematic review and evidence integration. Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT), Division of the National Toxicology Program (NTP), National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences, 2019. Available at: (https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/sites/default/files/ntp/ohat/pubs/handbookmarch2019_508.pdf).
- OECD (1998) OECD Principles on Good Laboratory Practice and Compliance Monitoring. Available at: (https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/1998/01/oecd-principles-on-good-laboratory-practice_g1gh32e8.html) (Accessed 07.01.2025).
- OECD, Guidance document on good in vitro method practices (GIVIMP). OECD Series on Testing and Assessment, No. 286, OECD Publishing, Paris, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304796-en>.
- M.J. Page, J.E. McKenzie, P.M. Bossuyt, I. Boutron, T.C. Hoffmann, C.D. Mulrow, et al., The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews, *BMJ* 2021;372 (2021) n71, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
- R. Pahwa, A. Goyal, I. Jialal, Chronic Inflammation. *StatPearls [Internet]*, StatPearls Publishing, Treasure Island (FL), 2023, 2024 Jan–. PMID: 29630225.
- M.D.J. Peters, C. Marnie, H. Colquhoun, et al., Scoping reviews: reinforcing and advancing the methodology and application, *Syst. Rev.* 10 (2021) 263, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01821-3>.
- G. Pizzino, N. Irrera, M. Cucinotta, G. Pallio, F. Mannino, V. Arcoraci, F. Squadrito, D. Altavilla, A. Bitto, Oxidative stress: Harms and benefits for human health, *Oxid. Med Cell Longev.* (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8416763>.
- S. Reuter, S.C. Gupta, M.M. Chaturvedi, B.B. Aggarwal, Oxidative stress, inflammation, and cancer: how are they linked? *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 49 (11) (2010) 1603–1616.
- J.M. Rice, Immunosuppression. Chapter 16. Tumour site concordance and mechanisms of carcinogenesis, in: R.A. Baan, B.W. Stewart, K. Straif (Eds.), IARC Scientific publication no. 165, IARC, Lyon, 2019.
- S. Romeo, A. Sannino, M.R. Scarfi, S. Lagorio, O. Zeni, Genotoxicity of radiofrequency electromagnetic fields on mammalian cells in vitro: A systematic review with narrative synthesis, *Environ. Int.* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.109104>.

- [36] S.W. Ryter, K. Mizumura, A.M.K. Choi, The impact of autophagy on cell death modalities, ID 502676, *Int. J. Cell Biol.* (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/502676>.
- [37] J.M. Samet, W.A. Chiu, V. Coglianò, J. Jinot, D. Kriebel, R.M. Lunn, F.A. Beland, L. Bero, P. Browne, L. Fritschi, The IARC monographs: updated procedures for modern and transparent evidence synthesis in cancer hazard identification, *JNCI: J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* 112 (2020) 30–37.
- [38] J.M. Sargeant, M.L. Brennan, A.M. O'Connor, Levels of evidence, quality assessment, and risk of bias: evaluating the internal validity of primary research ([Internet]), *Front. Vet. Sci.* 9 (2022) 1–8.
- [39] J.W. Shay, Role of telomeres and telomerase in aging and cancer, *Cancer Discov.* 6 (6) (2016) 584–593.
- [40] H. Sies, F. Ursini, Homeostatic control of redox status and health, *IUBMB Life* 74 (1) (2022) 24–28, <https://doi.org/10.1002/iub.2519>.
- [41] M. Simkó, D. Remondini, O. Zeni, M.R. Scarfi, Quality matters: systematic analysis of endpoints related to “cellular life” in vitro data of radiofrequency electromagnetic field exposure, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 13 (2016) 701.
- [42] Smith M.T. (2019). Key characteristics of carcinogens. Chapter 10. Tumour site concordance and mechanisms of carcinogenesis. IARC Scientific publication no. 165. Edited by Baan RA, Stewart BW, and Straif K. Lyon.
- [43] M.T. Smith, K.Z. Guyton, C.F. Gibbons, J.M. Fritz, C.J. Portier, I. Rusyn, et al., Key characteristics of carcinogens as a basis for organizing data on mechanisms of carcinogenesis, *Environ. Health Perspect.* 124 (6) (2016) 713–721, <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1509912>. PMID:26600562.
- [44] M.T. Smith, C.F. Skibola, J.M. Allan, G.J. Morgan, Causal models of leukaemia and lymphoma, *IARC Sci. Publ.* 157 (2004) 373–392.
- [45] A. Tubbs, A. Nussenzweig, Endogenous DNA damage as a source of genomic instability in cancer, *Cell* 168 (4) (2017) 644–656, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2017.01.002>.
- [46] Vijayalaxmi, T.J. Prihoda, Comprehensive review of quality of publications and meta-analysis of genetic damage in mammalian cells exposed to non-ionizing radiofrequency fields, *Rad. Res* 191 (2019) 20–30.
- [47] WHO. WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition, World Health Organization, Geneva, 2014. (https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/145714/9789241548960_eng.pdf?sequence=1) (Available at).
- [48] H. Zhao, L. Wu, G. Yan, Y. Chen, M. Zhou, Y. Wu, Y. Li, Inflammation and tumor progression: signaling pathways and targeted intervention, *12, Signal Transduct. Target Ther.* 6 (1) (2021) 263, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-021-00658-5>.